

FORMULATION AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT EVALUATION OF SUSTAINABLE PHBV/PBAT/RICE STRAW COMPOSITES

Laura Andrea Cabrera-Villamizar¹, Eugenia Núñez¹, Erlantz Lizundia², Amparo López-Rubio¹,
María José Fabra¹

¹Food Safety and Preservation Department, Institute of Agrochemistry and Food Technology (IATA-CSIC), Carrer del Catedràtic Agustín Escardino Benlloch, Spain

²Life Cycle Thinking Group, Department of Graphic Design and Engineering Projects, Faculty of Engineering in Bilbao. University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Bilbao, Spain. BCMaterials, Basque Center for Materials, Applications and Nanostructures, UPV/EHU Science Park, Leioa, Spain.

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la.cabrera10@iata.csic.es

Abstract: *As an alternative to conventional plastics, the formulation of biopolymeric composites, including biomass fillers, has gained attention in recent years (Phiri et al., 2023). This study focuses on formulating and characterizing biopolymeric composites, incorporating fillers obtained from residual biomasses as a potentially sustainable alternative to conventional plastics. Specifically, it showed novel composite materials that utilize rice straw (RS) as a filler in blends of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-valerate) (PHBV) and polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT). In addition to evaluating the physicochemical properties of these composites, the environmental impact (disintegration in soil, biodegradability, and life-cycle assessment (LCA)) was evaluated, contributing to the advancement of sustainable materials in the circular packaging sector. The research addresses the increasing demand for eco-friendly packaging solutions by exploring the use of agricultural waste as a functional filler in biopolymer composites.*

Composites were prepared by melt compounding followed by compression molding, with variations in PHBV:PBAT ratios (80:20, 50:50 and 20:80), RS particle size ($\leq 250 \mu\text{m}$ and $\leq 500 \mu\text{m}$), and RS concentration (20, 30, and 40%). The resulting materials were physicochemically characterized, showing that the polymer ratio and the RS concentration influenced the mechanical properties of the composites. In addition, the RS content results in significant color changes when using different particle sizes. FTIR analysis indicated that RS incorporation did not alter the chemical structure of the base polymers, suggesting a physical dispersion of the filler without forming new chemical interactions.

Thermal analysis (TGA and DSC) showed that RS incorporation generally decreased the thermal stability while the crystallization behavior was altered. Microstructural analysis revealed varying RS dispersion depending on the PHBV:PBAT ratio, with the 50:50 blend exhibiting a porous structure and poor dispersion. The water vapor permeability of the composites increased significantly in the 50:50 blend with the RS addition.

Biodegradability assessments included disintegration tests and biodegradation tests under industrial composting conditions. Only the 80:20 blends met ISO 20200:2016 standards for disintegration. Interestingly, biodegradation tests revealed lower biodegradation percentages for RS-containing 80:20 blends than the control. This discrepancy highlights the complex influence of environmental conditions and microbial communities on the degradation of RS-incorporated polymer blends. LCA was conducted to quantify the environmental impact of these novel materials. The cradle-to-grave analysis revealed a climate change potential for the composite films below the impact of commercial plastics based on fossil resources, underscoring the potential environmental benefits of these biodegradable composites.

This study highlights the potential of RS as a sustainable filler in biodegradable polymer composites for packaging applications. The results demonstrate that RS incorporation enhances mechanical properties while significantly reducing environmental impacts compared to conventional plastics. This research paves the way for valorizing agricultural waste in high-value applications, supporting circular economy principles, and promoting the transition to more sustainable packaging solutions.

REFERENCES

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